

CONSTRUCTION SECTOR AS AN INDICATOR OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN SERBIA

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Abstract: *The construction sector plays a very important role in shaping the economic landscape of a region. By building highways, residential units, commercial facilities, and public infrastructure, it is not only a significant contributor to GDP and employment but also a key indicator of infrastructural development, investment potential, and regional inequalities. This paper examines the connection between construction activities and regional development, focusing on selected European regions and the case of Serbia. Using statistical analysis and comparative insights, the study identifies regional differences, economic implications, and the sector's potential to promote sustainable and balanced territorial development. Special emphasis is placed on how construction activity correlates with socio-economic indicators such as wages, public investment, and local budgetary strength, making it a strategic tool for policy planning and regional cohesion.*

Keywords: *construction sector, regional development, Serbia, infrastructure, economic indicator*

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1. Introduction

Regional development is a multidimensional process that reflects the spatial distribution of economic activities, social well-being, and infrastructure across a country or group of countries. Balanced regional development is essential to achieving national cohesion, economic efficiency, and territorial equity. The construction sector, encompassing residential, commercial, industrial, and infrastructural development, plays a fundamental role in this process. It directly contributes to gross domestic product (GDP), generates employment, and enables the provision of essential public services such as transport, energy, education, and healthcare (OECD, 2021). The construction industry is frequently regarded as an indicator of economic activity due to its responsiveness to economic fluctuations and its significant connections with sectors such as manufacturing, real estate, and finance. Moreover, infrastructure development, most of which is delivered through construction, can reduce regional disparities by improving connectivity, facilitating business operations, and attracting investment (UN-Habitat, 2020). In developing and transition economies, including those in Southeast Europe, the construction industry is also a critical mechanism for post-conflict recovery, urban expansion, and the modernization of outdated infrastructure systems (World Bank, 2025). Despite its importance, the spatial distribution of construction activities is often uneven, reflecting broader patterns of regional inequality. Urban centres and capital regions typically experience higher levels of investment and construction output, while peripheral and rural areas lag behind. This paper explores how construction sector indicators can be used to assess and understand regional development trends, with a specific focus on the case of Serbia, which has pronounced regional disparities and ongoing infrastructural transformation.

This paper aims to analyze the connection between construction sector performance and regional development outcomes. The study will first present the theoretical and empirical background, then compare European regions. It will include a case study of Serbia to highlight specifics of regional development. The goal is to propose policy recommendations for using construction as a tool for achieving more balanced regional growth.

2. Theoretical background and literature review

The link between the construction sector and regional development has been extensively studied within the fields of regional economics, development studies, and urban planning. The theoretical foundation lies in the concept of economic base theory, which posits that regional development is primarily driven by activities that generate income from outside the region. Construction, particularly in infrastructure and housing, is considered a basic activity as far as it attracts external investment and enables further economic multipliers (Richardson, 1978). From a Keynesian perspective, construction plays a counter-cyclical role, as public investments in infrastructure are often increased during downturns to stimulate demand and create jobs (Arestis & Sawyer, 2003). Additionally, endogenous growth theory emphasizes the role of infrastructure in enhancing productivity, connectivity, and innovation, which are key factors in long-term regional competitiveness. (Barro & Sala-i-Martin, 2004). Empirical studies support these theoretical claims. For instance, Bottero et al. (2012) highlight how infrastructure investments contribute to spatial equity and economic cohesion in the European Union. Similarly, Crescenzi and Rodríguez-Pose (2012) argue that construction activities have a strong spillover effect, especially when aligned with broader regional development strategies.

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The World Economic Forum (2016) notes that construction serves as a foundation sector, affecting over 70% of global GDP when its indirect effects are considered. This significance is even more pronounced in countries undergoing transition or recovery, where public-private partnerships and strategic planning in construction can unlock regional potential (International Monetary Fund, 2018). In the Western Balkans, including Serbia, the construction sector has experienced fluctuating cycles of growth and contraction, influenced by political instability, EU integration processes, and macroeconomic reforms (World Bank, 2024). The regional disparity in construction output mirrors economic inequalities, where Belgrade and northern regions dominate, while southern and eastern Serbia remain underdeveloped (OECD, 2024). Indicators such as the number of building permits issued, the total value of completed construction works, and employment in the construction sector are commonly used to assess regional development progress. For instance, the Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia regularly publishes data on building permits, which serve as a proxy for construction activity and, by extension, regional economic health (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2025). However, scholars caution that relying solely on construction metrics may not adequately address structural disparities. Comprehensive regional development requires integrated policies encompassing education, governance, and innovation to ensure sustainable and equitable growth (Rodríguez-Pose, 2013). In the following paragraph something more will be said about the construction sector and regional development in Europe.

3. Construction Sector and Regional Development in Europe

The construction sector across European regions is characterized by diverse trends shaped by macroeconomic conditions, EU policy priorities, demographic shifts, and environmental imperatives. In recent decades, Europe has witnessed a structural transformation in construction activities, with increasing emphasis on sustainability, energy efficiency, and digitalization (Eurostat, 2024). Western and Northern Europe, particularly countries such as Germany, the Netherlands, and Sweden, exhibit high levels of construction output per capita, driven by strong economies, urban renewal programs, and green building initiatives. In contrast, Eastern and Southern European countries, including parts of the Balkans, continue to face challenges related to underinvestment, outdated infrastructure, and regulatory bottlenecks (European Construction Industry Federation, 2023).

A major driver of regional construction activity in Europe is the European Union's Cohesion Policy, which allocates significant funding for infrastructure and urban development, particularly in less-developed regions. For the 2021–2027 period, more than €370 billion is earmarked for reducing regional disparities, with construction playing a significant role in operational programs (European Commission, 2021). Another notable trend is the increasing role of public-private partnerships (PPPs) in financing and delivering construction projects. In countries such as France and the United Kingdom, PPPs have been used extensively to modernize transportation networks, social infrastructure, and energy systems. These arrangements help spread financial risks and accelerate project delivery, although concerns remain about transparency and long-term fiscal impacts (Grimsey & Lewis, 2005). Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic temporarily disrupted the construction sector across Europe, leading to project delays and labour shortages. However, recovery has been swift, particularly due to the EU Recovery and Resilience Facility, which includes substantial investment in green and digital construction projects aimed at fostering sustainable growth (OECD, 2022).

Regional disparities in construction activity often mirror broader socioeconomic inequalities. More developed regions typically attract higher levels of investment, leading to better infrastructure, more resilient housing, and stronger labour markets. Conversely, lagging regions often suffer from outdated facilities, limited housing supply, and slower project implementation rates (ESPON, 2020). As a result, construction policy must be integrated with broader regional development strategies to ensure balanced territorial growth.

4. Methodology and Data Sources

This study employs a quantitative research approach to assess the construction sector as an indicator of regional development, with a focus on Serbia's statistical regions. The analysis is based on secondary data obtained primarily from the Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, covering the most recent available year. The selected indicators include: Total and new construction works (in RSD thousand); Construction activity by type (buildings vs. civil engineering); Average net salaries and wages by region; Realized investments in new fixed assets; Total and per capita local government revenues and expenditures.

Regarding the data there is one issue that should be considered, and the best is to directly cite it: "Construction works value anticipates all construction materials applied, and labour force used. The value does not include the costs of land, project design, supervision and VAT. The value of works relates to undertakings in referent year, i.e. accomplished and unaccomplished constructions. The works executed were presented by territory where construction sites are found and not by territory, i.e. place where contractor's head office is situated." (Gavrilović, 2024, p. 238). Variables were analyzed across key Serbian regions, including Belgrade, Vojvodina, Šumadija and Western Serbia, Southern and Eastern Serbia, and selected major cities (Belgrade, Novi Sad, and Niš). The purpose was to examine potential correlations between construction output, income levels, investment patterns, and fiscal strength. Descriptive statistics and comparative analysis were applied to highlight regional disparities. The findings were visualized through summary tables and graphs to support interpretation and policy relevance. While the focus remains national, the broader conceptual framing is informed by literature on construction-driven development, spatial inequality, and infrastructure investment as a driver of regional cohesion.

5. Connection between construction sector and regional development in Serbia

The construction sector in Serbia plays a strategic role in supporting national economic growth and regional development. It contributes significantly to gross domestic product, employment, and investment, particularly in infrastructure, housing, and public services. In the past decade, Serbia has experienced a gradual revival of its construction industry, especially following the global financial crisis and more recently, the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia (2023), the construction sector accounted for approximately 6.2% of GDP in 2022, with over 120,000 employed persons. Regional disparities, however, remain notable. The Belgrade region has the highest construction output, followed by Vojvodina and Šumadija and Western Serbia, while Southern and Eastern Serbia have lower construction output. This spatial disparity highlights broader economic inequalities and uneven investment patterns across different regions. Government initiatives and foreign direct investment

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have significantly influenced construction activity. Major infrastructure projects such as the “Miloš Veliki” highway, the modernization of railway lines, and the Belgrade Waterfront urban redevelopment have attracted both domestic and international funding. These projects have contributed to the growth of the sector, particularly in urban centres and transit corridors (European Commission, 2020; European Commission, 2023). Public-private partnerships are also increasingly used as a mechanism to finance large-scale construction projects in Serbia. The legal framework has been enhanced since the adoption of the Law on Public-Private Partnerships and Concessions in 2011, aiming to attract private capital into public infrastructure. However, the implementation remains uneven across regions due to administrative capacity and investment attractiveness. Authors have been writing about this five years ago, also in the context of regional development: “Although the correlation between regional development and the number of approved PPP projects was not statistically significant at the regional level, a strong positive correlation was found at the district level, suggesting that more developed districts tend to attract a higher number of PPP projects” (Đorđević & Rakić, 2020, p. 176). This study proved the point of regionally uneven PPP projects implementation.

The analysis of the construction sector across Serbian regions provides important insights into its role as an indicator of regional development. Using recent data on construction activity, average salaries, local budget revenues and expenditures, as well as investments in fixed assets, several patterns become apparent that indicate the broader socio-economic differences between regions. The total value of construction works done in the Republic of Serbia amounts to approximately 717.5 billion RSD, of which more than 457.8 billion RSD is attributed to new construction projects. The leading contributor to this figure is the Vojvodina Region, with over 222 billion RSD in construction activity, followed by Belgrade Region and Šumadija and Western Serbia.

Figure 1: Value of Construction Works by Region (in million RSD)

Source: Authors representation based on data from Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia

The data on Figure 1 clearly shows that construction activities are heavily concentrated in economically dominant urban areas, particularly in the City of Belgrade and City of Novi Sad, with new construction forming a major part of total construction activities. For example, in Belgrade, approximately 125.7 billion RSD (over 61%) of total construction is new development, underlining the region's dynamism and continuous expansion. The structure of construction activities also reflects the economic roles of regions. In more developed regions, the ratio of buildings to civil engineering works is more balanced, while in peripheral regions like Šumadija and Western Serbia and Southern and Eastern Serbia, civil engineering (infrastructure) dominates, having more than twice the value of buildings. This is often related to state-led projects rather than private investment. This structural difference can be used to distinguish between regions developing organically through private construction markets and those reliant on public-sector infrastructure initiatives.

There is a visible correlation between regions with high construction output and higher average net salaries shown on Figure 2. The City of Belgrade reports the highest average salary of 109,431 RSD, while the City of Novi Sad follows with 101,101 RSD. These regions also have the most substantial construction output and investment volumes, suggesting a positive feedback loop where construction stimulates economic activity, increases employment, and boosts average income levels

Figure 2: Average Net Salaries vs. Construction Output by Region

Source: Authors representation based on data from Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia

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Regions such as Southern and Eastern Serbia, where average salaries fall below the national average (e.g., 73,373 RSD), show significantly lower levels of construction activity and civil engineering projects. This disparity further confirms the role of construction as both a driver and a reflection of regional economic vitality. When observing realized investments in new fixed assets, the capital regions again stand out, this can be seen in Table 1. The City of Belgrade accounts for nearly 693 billion RSD of such investments, indicating a strong pipeline of infrastructure and private sector developments. This is more than three times the investment seen in Southern and Eastern Serbia, despite the latter's larger geographical area and population. Additionally, data on budgetary receipts and expenditures per capita demonstrates similar trends. The City of Novi Sad and Belgrade report the highest per capita values (over 100,000 RSD), reflecting greater fiscal capacity and investment potential in urban centres. This financial capacity enables these urban centres to support further development initiatives, reinforcing regional advantages and creating conditions for sustained growth. On the other hand, less developed regions struggle with limited budgetary scope and consequently reduced public infrastructure investment.

Table 1: Local Budget Revenues and Expenditures, Realized Investments in new fixed assets by Region (Total and Per Capita)'

REGION	BUDGETARY RECEIPTS AND REVENUES TOTAL (in million RSD)	BUDGETARY RECEIPTS AND REVENUES per capita (in 1000 RSD)	BUDGETARY EXPENDITURES total (in million RSD)	BUDGETARY EXPENDITURES per capita (in 1000 RSD)	REALIZED INVESTMENTS IN NEW FIXED ASSETS Total (in million RSD)
Vojvodina	476.458093	71.938	475.413472	71.78	306.991475
Belgrade Region	134.674681	77.661	134.048597	77.3	693.280574
Šumadija and Western Serbia	162.971011	96.82	172.475404	102.467	200.798917
Southern and Eastern Serbia	98.20267	54.267	101.896352	56.308	213.903978
City of Belgrade	80.60973	57.734	66.993119	47.982	693.280574
City of Novi Sad	162.971011	96.82	172.475404	102.467	108.608081
City of Niš	40.899787	110.354	41.658801	112.402	14.880712

Source: Authors representation based on data from Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia

The construction sector in Serbia emerges as a robust and insightful indicator of regional development. Disparities in construction output, public investment, and wage levels closely mirror the broader socio-economic imbalances between regions. The analysis

confirms that areas with the highest construction activity, most notably Belgrade and Novi Sad, also enjoy higher average wages, stronger local budgetary capacities, and greater public investment. This correlation underscores the dual role of construction not only as a consequence of economic development but also as an active driver, capable of stimulating employment, enhancing infrastructure, and accelerating local economic growth. However, notable regional disparities persist, particularly in peripheral and less developed regions, where lower levels of construction activity coincide with weaker socio-economic performance. Bridging this gap requires targeted and well-coordinated policies aimed at decentralizing investment, strengthening regional planning capacities, and encouraging innovation within the construction sector.

An additional challenge in accurately assessing regional construction dynamics lies in the presence of “grey” construction, unregistered but not necessarily illegal activities, which remain outside the formal statistical records. This limits the precision of available data and highlights the need for improved regulatory oversight and data collection mechanisms.

Ultimately, stimulating construction in lagging regions could generate positive spillover effects in income growth, employment creation, and regional convergence. Strategic investments aligned with sustainable development goals, green building practices, and digital innovation can reinforce the role of the construction sector as a key pillar for achieving balanced and inclusive regional development in Serbia.

6. Conclusion

This paper has analyzed the construction sector as an indicator of regional development, emphasizing its macroeconomic importance and regional implications, with a special focus on Serbia. The findings indicate that the construction sector is very important in driving economic growth, advancing infrastructure, generating employment opportunities, and promoting spatial cohesion. As such, the sector is not only a reflection of national economic performance but also a driver of regional competitiveness and equity.

In Serbia, the construction industry has shown signs of resilience and transformation, supported by both public investment and private initiatives. However, significant regional disparities persist, with the capital region receiving a disproportionate share of construction activity. Addressing these imbalances requires strategic planning, improved administrative capacities at the local level, and enhanced use of instruments like public-private partnerships to mobilize investments outside core urban zones.

Detailed statistical analysis of Serbian regions supports these conclusions. Regions such as Belgrade and Novi Sad, which lead in total construction value, new construction activity, and realized investments, also show higher average salaries and stronger local budgetary revenues and expenditures. This alignment underscores the role of construction as both a consequence and the driver of regional prosperity. On the other hand, Southern and Eastern Serbia, along with parts of Western Serbia, lag significantly behind, indicating entrenched regional disparities. Thus, the construction sector can be considered not only a mirror but also a mechanism of regional development.

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Future development of the construction sector should increasingly align with sustainable practices, digital innovation, and the principles of green growth. This will be essential not only for environmental and social objectives but also for Serbia's integration into European markets and compliance with EU standards. Further research could explore the role of smart technologies, green building standards, and fiscal decentralization in supporting balanced regional construction development.

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GRAĐEVINSKI SEKTOR KAO INDIKATOR REGIONALNOG RAZVOJA U SRBIJI

Rezime: Građevinski sektor igra veoma važnu ulogu u oblikovanju ekonomskog pejzaža regiona. Izgradnjom autoputeva, stambenih jedinica, komercijalnih objekata i javne infrastrukture, on ne samo da značajno doprinosi BDP-u i zaposlenosti, već je i ključni pokazatelj razvoja infrastrukture, investicionog potencijala i regionalnih nejednakosti. Ovaj rad ispituje vezu između građevinskih aktivnosti i regionalnog razvoja, fokusirajući se na odabrane evropske regione i slučaj Srbije. Koristeći statističku analizu i uporedne uvide, studija identifikuje regionalne razlike, ekonomske implikacije i potencijal sektora za promociju održivog i uravnoteženog teritorijalnog razvoja. Poseban naglasak je stavljen na to kako se građevinska aktivnost povezuje sa socio-ekonomskim pokazateljima kao što su plate, javne investicije i lokalna budžetska snaga, što ga čini strateškim alatom za planiranje politika i regionalnu koheziju.

Ključne reči: građevinski sektor, regionalni razvoj, Srbija, infrastruktura, ekonomski indikatori